

D6.2: Project branding and project identity guide

TRANSFORM

Deliverable description

Deliverable:

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Due date:

30/04/2020

Actual submission date:

12/07/2021

Project start date:

01/01/2020

Duration:

36 months

Work Package concerned:

WP6

Concerned work package leader:

BE participation

Dissemination level:

PU: Public (must be available on the website)

CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CI: Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

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Revision history:

Version 1.0: final version submitted on 30/11/2020.

Version 1.2: revised version submitted on 12/07/2021 implementing modifications requested during the first project review process.

Disclaimer

This report reflects only the authors' view. The European Research Executive Agency (REA) and the European Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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Hello.

Welcome to TRANSFORM brand guidelines.

The following chapters contain the information and instructions for a correct use of the brand in different scenarios.

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The logo.

The symbol represents the transformative change process of the regions involved in the project, bringing together local decision makers, civil society organizations (representing society), universities/research centers, and local companies working together towards implementing RRI in their territorial R&I strategies.

TRANSFORM

Symbol

Symbol + Wordmark

Alternative version.

The horizontal version is required when the space available is low and wide.

TRANSFORM

Colours.

This is the primary colour palette for the logo.

PANTONE Black C
C 0, M 0, Y 0, K 100
#200000

PANTONE 604 C
C 7, M 4, Y 88, K 0
#F4E239

PANTONE 7409 C
C 3, M 30, Y 97, K 0
#F6B627

PANTONE 158 C
C 0, M 66, Y 99, K 0
#F37723

PANTONE 485 C
C 1, M 99, Y 95, K 0
#EC2027

PANTONE 1925 C
C 1, M 98, Y 62, K 0
#ED1E4F

PANTONE 213 C
C 1, M 99, Y 29, K 0
#EB1670

PANTONE 219 C
C 2, M 98, Y 2, K 0
#E9158B

PANTONE 7655 C
C 23, M 73, Y 2, K 0
#C164A4

PANTONE 271 C
C 47, M 44, Y 1, K 0
#8C8BC1

PANTONE 298 C
C 70, M 16, Y 0, K 0
#29AAE1

PANTONE 564 C
C 50, M 6, Y 26, K 0
#7FC2C0

PANTONE 365 C
C 26, M 2, Y 61, K 0
#C3D986

Monochrome version.

When you are required to print in one colour, you can use the black or white colour versions.

Typography I.

The font used in the logo is Novecento Sans Normal.

TRANSFORM

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

0123456789

Typography II.

For headlines, callouts and tagline, the font to be utilised is Fira Sans Bold.

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNPOQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789

For subheading, the font to be utilised is Fira Sans Light Italic.

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNPOQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789

For body copy, quotes and other collateral, the font to be utilised is Fira Sans Light. The whole typeface may be used if necessary.

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNPOQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789

Download the font by clicking here:

<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Fira+Sans>

and install them on your computer.

Exclusion area.

The exclusion area is the space around the logo which must remain free from other elements to ensure that the logo is not obscured.

Minimum size.

This is the minimum size the logo should have for printing purposes and for the web.
Never change the proportions when resizing it.

Digital: 100 px width
Print: 1 cm width

TRANSFORM

Digital: 170 px width
Print: 1,7 cm width

TRANSFORM

Digital: 283 px width
Print: 2,8 cm width

Placement on different backgrounds I.

Use the multicolor logo over images and colored backgrounds always with a white circle underneath. When placing over white background the white circle is not necessary. Some examples:

Placement on different backgrounds II.

The monochrome version logo is ideal for use over images and colored backgrounds. When placing over photography, ensure contrast by placing the logo in white color over dark area or the logo in black color over bright area. Some examples:

Logo declinations.

A set of declinations of the TRANSFORM logo have been created to represent the four territories involved in the project, based on each region/city's flag colours and structure. The regional TRANSFORM logo versions can be used for cluster-specific materials or events, as well on the project website.

TRANSFORM
BRUSSELS

TRANSFORM
LOMBARDY

TRANSFORM
CATALONIA

TRANSFORM
BOSTON

Logo declinations • Brussels.

Primary version

Horizontal version

Logo declinations • Lombardy.

TRANSFORM
LOMBARDY

Primary version

TRANSFORM
LOMBARDY

Horizontal version

Logo declinations • Catalonia.

TRANSFORM
CATALONIA

Primary version

TRANSFORM
CATALONIA

Horizontal version

Logo declinations • Boston.

TRANSFORM
BOSTON

Primary version

TRANSFORM
BOSTON

Horizontal version

Information on EU funding.

Obligation and right to use the EU emblem

Unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic), communication activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must:

- (a) display the EU emblem and**
- (b) include the following text:**

For dissemination of results and communication activities:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 872687”.

For infrastructure, equipment and major results:

“This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 872687”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Agency.

This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

Files available for download:

https://europa.eu/european-union/about-eu/symbols/flag_en

www.transform-project.eu

 @TRANSFORM_eu

 TRANSFORM project group

 TRANSFORM project

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